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INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY IN MICRO FINANCIAL SERVICES IN INDIA

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ABSTRACT

Microfinance means providing very poor families with very small loans (micro credit) to help them engage in productive activities /small businesses. Over time, microfinance has come to include a broader range of services (credit, savings, insurance, etc.). the poor and the very poor who lack access to traditional formal financial institutions require a variety of financial products. In order to enable the poor people to access credit , there is a need to strengthen all the available channels of providing credit to the poor. such as Micro Finance Institutions , Cooperative Banks, State financial corporations, Regional Rural Banks and Primary Agricultural Credit Societies. This paper explore the major initiative for development of micro finance in India.

Key words: Micro finance, Information Technology, micro credit

INTRODUCTION:

The poor in India do not have adequate access to the formal banking sector. The credit requirement of the poor in India has been estimated by the World Bank to be around Rs.50,000 crore per annum in 2002. Against this requirement, the credit outstanding of the poor with the formal banking sector is stated to be Rs.5000 crore or ten per cent of the total demand.

The poor require finance for both production and consumption purposes. Production loan may be of three types, viz. (a) short term (for periods up to 15 months), (b) medium term (from 15 months to 5 years) and (c) long term (for periods above five years). Economic activity in rural areas may relate to the various sectors of crop husbandry, animal husbandry, poultry, fishery, cottage & village industries, handicrafts, transportation, repair shops, and trade & services. But the recent strategy is to ensure flexibility in lending and in repayment based on the capacity of the borrower to earn enough to repay- whether it is daily, weekly, monthly or seasonal. Short term loans may be required by the poor for purchasing (HYV) seeds, fertilizer and for irrigating a leased-in land etc. Medium term loans may be required for purchase of bullocks (or a boat) and for purchase of machinery and equipment. Long term loans may be required for repayment of loans, for constructing a shed/shop and for

purchase of land etc. What needs to be appreciated is that all the three kinds of production loans are relevant to the poor.

Availability of finance, moreover, tilts the employment scenario in favour of self-employment vis-à-vis wage employment. An added dimension is the empowerment of women with easier availability of micro-finance to them. Going by the estimates provided earlier, the demand for production credit in the country today is equal to Rs.17000 crore per annum whereas the total credit outstanding under micro-finance is merely Rs.5000 crore. Thus, there is definitely a need to increase the flow of credit, both for consumption and production, to the rural sector.

Objective:

To explore the major initiative for development of micro finance in India

To analyse the role of technology in execution of Micro financial services

Major initiatives

Government's initiative to reduce poverty by improving access to financial services to poor started since independence. India's overwhelming majority of poor is located in rural areas and this motivated the government to give special attention to rural credit. Following the report of All India Rural Credit Survey in mid 1950's, the State took crucial steps in reviewing Cooperative structure including the partnership of State in cooperatives. Also the policy initiative of 'social banking' concept described as "the elevation of the entitlements of previously disadvantaged groups to formal credit even if this may entail a weakening of the conventional banking practices" led to the nationalisation of commercial banks in 1969, adoption of direct lending programmes to rural areas and development of credit institutions such as Regional Rural Banks (RRBs). Government initiatives during the Fourth Plan focused on marginal farmers and agricultural labourers bringing individual family as the basic borrowing unit. Integrated sustainable income generating activity was promoted through subsidized lending under Integrated Rural Development Programme (IRDP) and its subsequent variations including the current self-employment programme known as Swaranjayanti Gram Swarozgar Yojana (SGSY).

Shivaraman Committee (1978)

Looking into all aspects of consumption credit for the poor, the Expert Committee on Consumption Credit (Chairman: Shri B. Shivaraman, Member, Planning Commission) recommended for allowing a line of credit to poor households by the formal banking sector. Examining the consumption need of the poor in 1976, the Committee recommended a line of credit equal to Rs.750 per household. The specific consumption demands identified by the Committee were: (a) medical expenses (33%), (b) marriage (33%), (c) education (13%), (d) birth, death & religious purposes (10%) and (e) general consumption (10%).

The co-operative credit structure was to be the main pillar of this drive. The Committee further recommended for legislative reforms in all states for universal membership in all the Primary Agricultural Cooperative Credit Societies (PACS) across the country. In regard to the rate of interest, the Committee observed that the rate charged by both cooperative banks and commercial banks on consumption loans should be the same as crop loans. It further observed, 'The cost of servicing the consumption loans will perhaps be even higher than the agricultural loans, therefore, to expect the societies to operate on smaller margins than on the agricultural loans will be unrealistic'.

On the premise that the risk to the banking sector in the case of consumption loan is higher than the production loan, the Committee recommended for a higher percentage (10%) of risk cover by the Government than usually done for other (rural) loans extended by the co-operative and commercial banks. On the estimated demand for consumption loan of Rs.170 crore (in 1976), it provided for Rs.17 crore as Risk Fund. This fund, moreover, was required to be shared equally by the Central and the State Governments.

However, despite all its moorings there was not much progress in regard to flow of consumption credit to the poor by the formal banking sector. Legislative reforms vis-à-vis universal membership in PACS was introduced; but the co-operative banks themselves became weaker and weaker in the subsequent years. The introduction of bank-SHG linkage programme in the 1990's has in some ways addressed the need of consumption credit of the poor. Under this system, the banks lend to the SHGs who, in turn, are free to disburse loan to their members in their best judgement, whether for production or for consumption purposes.

Reserve Bank of India's All India Rural Credit Surveys

The All India Rural Credit Surveys conducted by the RBI during the various years, show the following transformation in rural credit, viz.,

- (i) The share of non-institutional sector in rural credit that was 91 per cent in 1951 went down to 45 per cent in 1991.
- (ii) The share of institutional sector that stood at 9 per cent in 1951 went up to 53 per cent in 1991.
- (iii) The share of credit cooperatives in rural credit that was 4.6 per cent in 1951 went up to 29 per cent in 1981, but declined subsequently to 19 per cent in 1991.
- (iv) The share of commercial banks in rural credit that was 1.1 per cent in 1951 went up to 29 per cent in 1981 and has remained at the same level in 1991.

The above mentioned percentages are, however, based on aggregate figures and do not throw much light in regard to transformation in rural credit vis-à-vis micro-finance. There has not been any rural credit survey at the all-India level since 1991. A survey was, nevertheless organised by the World Bank & NCAER in 2003. It utilised a sample of 6000 households (in Andhra Pradesh and Uttar Pradesh) and throws light on the condition of micro-finance as well. According to this study, around 87 per cent of marginal farmers /landless labourers do not access credit from the formal banking sector. In other words, the share of non-institutional sector in micro-credit remains, more or less, the same as during 1951. Most of the benefits of the so called extensive banking infrastructure have gone to the relatively better-off people; around 66 per cent of large farmers have a deposit account and 44 per cent have access to credit.

Formal/Banking sector initiatives

Various programmes were initiated by banks to inculcate savings habit and to provide financial assistance. The initiatives are as follows-

1. Pigmy deposit scheme – The Pigmy deposit scheme intended to collect tiny deposits from the depositors from their doorsteps. The scheme was implemented by a few banks by engaging local people. The experience of the banks was not encouraging as there were large scale cash leakages, frauds and reconciliation problems. Most banks found the scheme unattractive.
2. Mobile banks – Some of the banks started mobile banks in rural areas. The location and time of operation are usually synchronized with the market days so that the large

number of people could transact its business. This programme was dropped because of the man power constraints.

3. Regional Rural Banks (RRBs) were intended to serve the people not covered by co-operatives and commercial banks. But they were not able to serve the purpose as they were more focused on profitability and strong balance-sheets. In spite of this, it was found that the RRBs are better equipped than the commercial and co-operative banks to undertake micro finance operations because of the understanding of the local conditions. As on 2005, there were 196 RRBs, covering 516 districts and a client base of 6.27 crore.
4. Local area banks (LABs) aimed to mobilize rural savings by local institutions and makes them available for investment locally. They were set up in private sector and regulated by RBI. The working of LABs was not very encouraging. One serious drawback was absence of refinancing facility. Krishna Bhima Samrudi, the local area bank in Andhra Pradesh is only one into the business of micro finance on a large scale.

Self Help Groups (SHGs)

Government initiatives during seventies and the Fourth Five Year Plan focussed on small and marginal farmers and agricultural labourers. Integrated sustainable income generation activity was promoted under Integrated Rural Development Programme. Inadequacies inherent in running programs focussed on individual households called for shift to a group based approach. The first step towards setting up self help groups (SHGs) was taken by MYRADA and it built upon rural chit funds and informal lending networks to evolve a credit management group.

National Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development

In 1991-92, NABARD launched the SHG-Bank Linkage Programme on a pilot basis to finance SHGs across the country through the formal banking system. High repayment rates by the SHGs encouraged the banks to finance SHGs.

Rashtriya Mahila Kosh (RMK),1993

The success of the concept of micro-credit through self help groups (SHGs) has encouraged the Government of India to establish a National level Micro-Credit organization /Rashtriya Mahila Kosh (RMK) (National Credit Fund for Women) under the Ministry of Women and Child Development in 1993, with an initial corpus of Rs.31 crore. The objective was to help women organise income generating activities to improve their socio economics status. RMK had disbursed cumulative loan of Rs 151 crore up to July 2006, benefiting 5.50 lakh women and the recovery rate is above 91%.

Small Industries Development Bank of India (SIDBI), 1994

In 1994, Small Industries Development Bank of India (SIDBI) launched a pilot scheme to provide financial assistance by way of loans to NGO's for providing credit to the poor households, especially women. A small amount of grant also accompanied the loans so as to build capacity of the intermediates and end-users. The programme did not achieve the desired objective. A large number of NGOs were not able to up scale their lending operations because of difficulties like interest rate cap on lending, security stipulations etc. SIDBI reoriented its Micro Finance Programme in 1999 by addressing the weakness of the pilot scheme, with an objective to create a national network of large and viable Micro Finance Institutions from the formal and informal sector. The programme provides need based assistance by way of term loans to partner institutions for meeting their on lending fund requirements. Its programme took off slowly. The bank was able to improve its portfolio by 100% each year for the last three years in a row. It had sanctioned Rs.320 crore financial assistance during 2006 as against Rs 189.73 crore during 2005.

SHG-Bank Linkage Programme (1996)

In 1996, Reserve Bank of India included financing of SHGs as a main stream activity of banks under the priority sector lending programmes. The SHG Bank linkage programme covered over 24.3 million families by March 2005. Under the Bank-SHG Linkage Programme 2.24 million SHGs were linked, up to 31st March 2006, of which 90 percent are women's groups.

Microfinance Development and Equity Fund (MD & EF), 2001

Government of India, in 2001 re-designated the existing Micro Finance Development Fund as Micro Finance Development and Equity Fund with the objective of facilitating and supporting the orderly growth of the microfinance sector, by especially assisting the women and vulnerable sections of the society and also by supporting their capacity building. The

size of the fund was also enhanced from the existing Rs.100 crore to Rs.200 crore. The additional amount was to be contributed by Reserve Bank of India, NABARD and the commercial banks in the proportion 40:20:20.

Micro Finance Programme(MFC), 2004

In March 2004, the Ministry of Small Scale Industry introduced the Micro Finance Programme along with the SIDBI. The Government provides funds for Micro Finance Programme to SIDBI, called “Portfolio Risk Fund (PRF)”. This fund is used for security deposit required of the MFIs/ NGOs to get loan. At present SIDBI takes fixed deposit equal to 10% of the loan amount. The share of MFIs/ NGOs is 2.5% of the loan amount (i.e 25% of security deposit) and balance 7.5 % (i.e 75% of security deposit) is adjusted from the funds provided by the Government of India. The MFIs/ NGOs avail of loan from SIDBI for further on lending on the support of the deposit. Upto December 2006, 39 MFIs have been disbursed loan to the tune of Rs. 102 crore, thereby utilizing an amount of Rs.7.64 crore from the PRF. This has benefited approximately 3.20 lakh beneficiaries, mainly women.

Micro Finance Bill (2006)

The Micro Financial Sector (Development & Regulation) Bill was recently introduced in the Parliament. The salient features of the draft Micro Finance Bill (2006) are as follows:

- (a) Enactment of the bill will give the NABARD explicit powers to regulate the micro finance and so ensure greater transparency, effective management and better governance. This will facilitate the flow of Micro Finance Services in a more efficient way to the un-banked population.
- (b) The Bill defines the Micro Finance services as provision of financial assistance to the eligible clients either directly or through group mechanism for small and tiny enterprise, agriculture, allied activities including consumption, upto an amount not exceeding Rs. 50,000/- in aggregate and upto Rs. 1,50,000/- for housing purpose or such other amounts for the above purpose or such other purposes as specified by the NABARD from time to time.
- (c) Micro Finance Organization is defined as an Organization carrying on the business of extending Micro Finance Services and includes Society registered under the Societies Registration Act, 1860 or a Trust created under the Indian Trust Act, 1880 or Public Trust registered under any State enactment or a Cooperative Society engaged in Micro

Finance service excluding a Cooperative Bank as defined under the Banking Regulation Act, 1949.

- (d) It differentiates between Organizations accepting thrift and those not accepting thrift. Thrift receiving organizations will be kept under sharp focus. No micro finance Organization would be able to accept thrift unless it obtains a certificate of registration from the NABARD subject to fulfilment of certain conditions. It will require MFOs accepting thrift to create a Reserve Fund.
- (e) It provides for the creation of a Micro Finance Development Council for advising the NABARD on formulation policies.
- (f) It provides to facilitate constitution of a Micro Finance Development and Equity Fund to provide loans, refinance, grant and seed capital to MFOs.
- (g) It will provide a redressal mechanism through a Scheme of Micro Finance Ombudsman.
- (h) It will provide penalties for violation on the provisions of the Act.
- (i) It will authorise the Central government to make rules and authorise the NABARD to formulate regulations with the previous approval of Central Government.

Role of Technology and Micro-Finance

Micro-finance is not only about credit. It is as much about thrift (or savings), remittance services and micro-insurance. In a way, even credit may be looked at as one's own savings made available at advance. There is need to put in place a workable system, technologically and managerially, for collecting savings from the poor in small amounts, at regular intervals and at their door step. In the case of the urban poor, in particular, it is observed that they suffer from high income drain on account of many avoidable practices. There is, as such, a great need for plugging this income drain through diverting their resources to savings. The economically active urban poor may be encouraged to own 'debit card' and banks may introduce ATM machines in the residential colonies of the poor. Besides this, the urban wage earners separated from their rural families require to send money home. NBFC-MFI network could devise a mechanism to deliver the money at their doorstep. There are, similarly, many upcoming technologies suitable for the rural poor. 'Gramteller', a rural ATM could be explored for their successful usability in rural areas. Introduction of (bio-metric) smart cards is also expected to revolutionise the micro-finance sector and bring down the transaction costs.

Information and Communication Technology (ICTs) and Micro- Finance Activities.

ICTs can be effectively used to provide information about micro finance organisations and their services. Though many web sites provide information on micro financing, there is dearth of information on the terms and conditions, institutions that provides micro finance etc. This information can be provided both in English and also in other Indian languages.

ICTs can be used to provide access to wider markets and better prices. ICTs can be used to enhanced the economic returns for the micro finance activities by provide access to global markets at better prices. At present RURALBAZAR ([http:// ruralbazar.nic.in](http://ruralbazar.nic.in)) the application software has been conceptualized to assist market needs of products produced by rural people. It offers internet web to show case there products to the world. It appears some of the states like Tamil Nadu, Goa and Tripura have successfully adopted the software. However, efforts should be made to ensure quality of the products produced by rural producers and to provide logistic support like appropriate packages and timely delivery to the products.

Common Service Centres

Department of Information Technology, Government of India has proposed to set up a network of more than 100000 internet enabled Information and Communication Technology (ICT) access points termed as Common Service Centres (CSC). They are meant to provide high quality and cost effective video, voice and data content by the end of 2007. The Goal is to empower the rural community and catalyze social change through modern technologies. It endeavours to provide economical access to information and services to rural citizens and improve governance at cheaper cost. It envisages a collaborating model that allows public and private enterprises to integrate their goals of profit and social objective into a sustainable business model for achieving rapid socio-economic change. The scheme proposes a three tier structure where at the first level a Village Level Entrepreneur (VLE- a franchise), at the middle level a Service Centre Agency (SCA- franchiser) and at the third level a State Level Agency (SLA) to facilitate implementation of the scheme with in the state. The SLA will be responsible for implementation of the scheme through the franchiser (SCA) and the franchisee (VLE).

CONCLUSION:

The positive result of the growth of self help groups is an increased availability of credit to poor household in rural areas. However, the poorest households are still not able to access credit and assistance provided by government programmes. They are not able to improve their income earning capacity by acquiring the right kind of assets or selecting the most suitable activity. Impact assessment studies of the schemes implemented by the Ministry of Rural Development confirm the benefits of self employment programmes accrue to slightly better off rural households

The poor people's access to credit may be significantly improved through all the channels of SHG-Bank linkage programme, MFIs, Cooperative Banks, State Financial Corporations, RRB s and PACS. Some MFIs (i.e. Grameen Bank model/LABS, NBFCs) have been doing very well in selected states with dynamic markets and dynamic individuals. Beyond these jurisdictions, their outreach is non-existent. Any significant up scaling of micro-finance at the all India level will have to depend, therefore, on the large network of banks, the bank-SHG linkage programme and the MFIs. In addition, the post office network in the country may also be used to deliver banking services, especially in remote rural areas. The post offices may be further encouraged to work as "business facilitator" and as "banking correspondent" in accordance with RBI guidelines. The NABARD may consider setting up a Committee, consisting of various private and public sector banks, the Ministry of Rural Development, Small Industries Development Organisation (SIDO) of Ministry of Small Scale Industries (SSI), Rashtriya Mahila Kosh (RMK) of The Ministry of Women and Child Development, Department of Posts, SIDBI, MFIs and the NGOs in the micro finance sector to evolve an effective strategy to implement the Business Facilitators and Correspondents Model. Such a strategy should also take into account special target groups such as the SCs/STs and the minorities through their respective National Finance Corporations. The Eleventh Plan may target to extend micro-finance to at least 80 percent of the BPL households.

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